

ROLE OF COCKROACHES IN PARASITIC DISEASE TRANSMISSION IN AMORKA, IHIALA LGA

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ABSTRACT	KEYWORDS
<p>Cockroaches are omnivorous insects with nocturnal and unsanitary habits, making them efficient mechanical vectors of various pathogenic agents. They contaminate food, utensils, and human environments, contributing to the transmission of bacteria, fungi, protozoa, viruses, and helminth parasites. Diseases associated with these pathogens, including Ascariasis, Amebiasis, Giardiasis, and other intestinal disorders, pose significant public health challenges, particularly in areas with poor hygiene and sanitation. This study investigated the parasites harbored by cockroaches in Amorka, Ihiala Local Government Area, Anambra State, Nigeria, aiming to identify species of public health importance and assess their potential role in disease transmission. Findings from this research provide baseline data that can inform community education and control strategies to mitigate the risks of cockroach-borne parasitic infections.</p>	<p>Cockroaches, Parasite Transmission, Public Health, Mechanical Vector, Amorka, Nigeria.</p>

1. Introduction

Opportunities to disseminate pathogenic agents on food Cockroaches play an important role in transmitting different resources. They are nocturnal and have filthy habits which diseases transmission either mechanically or occasionally coupled with their feeding mechanisms make them efficient biologically. They belong to insects being the most successful vectors of pathogen like bacteria (*klebsiella pnenmonia*, animals in the world because of their ability to adapt in various *Enterobacter cloacae*, *Enterobacteraerogenes*, *salmonella* environmental conditions. There are approximately 3500 spp, *Sshigellasonnei*, *Vibro cholera*, *Citrobacter freundii*) species of cockroaches worldwide. Among these species thirty (Bradman, 2017 and Bamigboye, 2016), fungi (*Candida spp*, are associated with human habitations (Mbanugo and Abazie, *Rhizopus spp*, *Mucor spp*) (Hamu, 2014), eggs of some 2002 and Adeleke, 2016). The majority of these species live pathogenic intestinal worm (Hook worm, *Taxocaracanis*, in tropical and subtropical areas where they are abundantly *Hymenolepis nana* and *Strongyloides stercolaris larvae*), found in areas with frequent stagnant water bodies or with a viruses (*Poliomyelitis*), protozoa (Oocysts of *Isospora belli*, constant and high moisture availability such as pit latrine, *Balantidium coli*,

Cryptosporidium parvum and kitchen, sewage and drainages where water serve as migration *Giardialambilia*) (Ekesiobi and Igbodika, 2015).

Routes from place to place (Hamu, 2014). In addition to their repulsive and annoying characteristics, they eat and Diseases associated with these parasites, such as *Ascariasis*, contaminate food and leave a persistent offensive odor in *Ameobiasis*, *Giardiasis*, cause liver complications, stunted infested places. Cockroaches are omnivorous and eat anything growth, chronic diarrhea and intestinal disturbances; pose organic, frequently feed on human faces, garbage and sewage serious public problems especially in poor areas, where there (Bala and Sule, 2017). Therefore they have copious is lack of proper hygiene to control the spread (Mbanugo and Abezie, 2014; Ekesiobi et al., 2024; Abiodun *et al.*, 2025). Cockroaches vomit and defecate on exposed foods, which can easily be transmitted to humans when they feed on these contaminated food. They are also the major sources of indoor allergens. Exposure and sensitization to cockroach allergens are associated with asthma related health problems (Hamu, 2014).

Cockroaches are abundant in most homes in Nigeria (Bala and Sure, 2017). The risk to human health arising from cockroach infestation have been reported due to inadequate accommodation and lack of adequate maintenance of existing facilities. High incidence of pest infestation occurs, arising from poor hygiene, improper storage and disposal of waste (Bradman, 2017 and Bamigboye, 2016). Therefore this study was carried out to identify and isolate parasites infested on cockroaches which transmit parasitic diseases in Amorka, Ihiala Local Government Area, Anambra State. The findings would be of benefits to the residents of the area within or outside Nigeria, as it will help to educate them on the dangers posed to them by the presence of cockroaches in their houses. The behavior, feeding habits and mobility of cockroaches makes them well adapted for mechanical transmission of oocytes, cyst and larvae of parasites that causes diseases whose epidemiology are still poorly understood in developing countries. This may be due to the presence of the parasites in the stool, lack of documentation, under or over reporting of episodes due to inaccurate diagnosis, different level of hygiene and sanitation as well as different socio-economic status of people.

There is increase in cockroach population in areas with poor sanitary conditions in Nigeria. The risk to human health arising from cockroach infestation have been reported as c cockroaches are known mechanical vectors of human pathogens and there are reports of the isolation of various pathogenic human helminthes and protozoan parasites from them.

There is lack of information on the role of cockroaches in the mechanical transmission of parasites in Amorka community, hence the need for this research work. The result of this study will provide base line data on the parasites of public health importance that Can be mechanically vectored by cockroaches to man.

2. Materials and Methods

Description of study area

Amorka is a town in the Ihiala government area of Anambra State of Nigeria. It is located along the Onitsha-Owerri Expressway, on the border of Mgbidi Imo State. Amorka is a home to the former Biafra Airport stripes. Amorka is a home to a famous Bunker of Dim Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu during the Biafra war and still exists. The town consists of eight villages: Ikenga, Umuanum, Umuejim, Umueze, Umuezeala, Umuezike,

Umunakwa, and Umuokpara. Biafra Airport is located in Amorka; it is currently owned by the Abalobi family. Its neighboring towns include Uli, Ibiasoegbe, Mgbedi, Ozara, Ohakpu, Egbu, and Olu. Its geographical coordinates are 5.7320° N, 6.8735° E. Its postal code is 431125.

Sampling population and collection

A total of 350 cockroaches 298 adults and 52 nymph were caught from 20 different houses randomly selected in Amorka from different villages. The cockroaches were caught using an insecticides and also by wearing a sterile hand glove in collecting them. The location for setting the traps were in the dark and humid places inside the premises especially at the kitchen, pit latrine and rooms. The cockroaches were separated and were put into airtight containers according to the site of collection where the cockroaches were caught to prevent any cross contamination that might tamper with results.

Sampling techniques, Identification and Isolation

The containers with the samples were taken to the Laboratory of Biological science department, Chukwuemeka Odumegwu Ojukwu University for processing. The collected samples were killed slowly using chloroform. The cockroaches were washed by manual shaking for 1 minute using formal detergent technique. The cockroaches were washed with 5 ml of formalin-detergent solution (1ml of detergent + 1ml of formaldehyde + 48ml of distilled water), properly mixed and dispensed into a centrifuge tube and spun for 10 minutes at 2000rpm. The residue was mixed and poured on a dry clean slide, cover slip applied and stained with Lugol's iodine and the slide microscopically examined using x40 objective lens. The parasites and their stages encountered were identified.

Parasitological technique.

Two types of staining techniques were used for microscopic examination namely by using 1% Lugol's iodine was used to enhance the image of the helminths ova. The sediments obtained from the sedimentation by centrifugation were collected using sterile pasture pipettes. Iodine were mixed thoroughly using another sterile Pasteur pipette before it was covered with the slip. The sterilized solution was examined under the light microscope under a magnification of 100x and 40x objectives.

Statistical Analysis of Data

3. Results

Data obtained in the study were analyzed statistically using Chi Square test at $p < 0.05$ significant level.

A total of 350 cockroaches were studied, all were identified as *Periplaneta americanus* 286 (32.17%) and *Blatta orientalis* 64 (18.75), males 190 (25.26%) and female 160 (35.00%), adult were 298 (31.54%) and nymph 52 (19.23%). The result shows that out of the total number of cockroaches, 350 caught and examined for the presence of parasitic stages, 104 were contaminated with the different stages of the parasites.

In table 1, the total number of *Periplaneta americanus* is 286 which were all examined and 92(32.71%) were found to be contaminated with parasites, while the total number of *Blatta orientalis* is 64 which were also all examined and 12(18.75%) were found to be contaminated with parasites.

The difference in the infestation rate was analyzed statically and found to be significant ($p < 0.05$).

Table 1: Number of contaminated cockroaches in the study area.

Cockroach Species	Number Examined	Number Positive	Percentage Infested %
<i>Periplaneta americanus</i>	286	92	32.17
<i>Blatta orientalis</i>	64	12	18.75
Total	350	104	29.71

In table 2, total number of males examined were 190 and 48(25.26%) was infested with parasites. Total number examined of female is 160 and 56(35.00%) was found to be infested with the parasites. The difference in the rate of infestation was statically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Table 2: Distribution of parasites by gender of cockroach in the study area.

Cockroach Gender	Number Examined	Number Positive	Percentage Infested %
Males	190	48	25.26
Females	160	56	35.00
Total	350	104	29.71

Table 3: Abundance and rate of contamination of parasitic cockroaches in relation to sampling sites.

Sampling Site	Number Examined	Number Positive	Percentage Infested %
Pit Latrine	187	71	37.97
Living Room	61	12	19.67
Kitchen	102	21	20.59
Total	350	104	29.71

In table 4, 94 (31.54%) of adult cockroaches were contaminated more than nymphs, 10 (19.23%).

The difference in the rate of infection was statistically not significant ($p > 0.05$). The observed difference may have occurred by chance.

Table 4: Abundance of parasites on the different developmental stages of the cockroaches in the study area.

Sampling Sites	Number Examined	<i>Entamoeba histolytica</i> (%)	<i>Ascaris lumbricoides</i> (%)	<i>Trichuris trichiura</i> (%)	Hook Worm (%)	Total (%)
Pit Latrine	187	31(16.58)	27(14.44)	4(2.17)	9(4.81)	71(37.97)
Living Room	61	7(11.48)	4(6.56)	1(1.64)	0(0)	12(19.67)
Kitchen	102	9(8.82)	6(5.88)	4(3.92)	2(1.96)	21(20.59)
Total	350	47(13.43)	37(10.57)	9(2.57)	11(3.14)	104(29.71)

Developmental Stages	Number Examined	Number Positive	Percentage Infested %
Adult	298	94	31.54
Nymph	52	10	19.23
Total	350	104	29.71

In table 5, *Entamoeba histolytica* recorded the highest 47(13.43%) followed by *Ascaris lumbricoides* 37(10.57%), hook worm 11(3.14%), *Trichuris trichiura* 9(2.57%).

The difference in the rate of infection was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$).

Table 5: Abundance of helminthes and protozoan parasites among the cockroaches in relation to sampling sites.

4. Discussion

The result of this study showed the different developmental stages of cockroaches were contaminated by different stages of parasites and these cockroaches also have the ability of transmitting parasitic infections. Therefore the control measures should target both stages. The female (35.00%) cockroaches were significantly more infested

than the male ($P < 0.05$). (25.26%), from observation the female roam about more than the male in search for food and site to lay eggs, by doing so they come in contact with contaminated fecal materials and mechanically carry the parasites recorded. The overall parasite contamination rate 29.71% recorded in this study disagreed with the study of Chamirat (2012) who recorded 54.1%, Ajero (2011) 67%, Almayali and Alyagoobi (2010) 83.33% and Bala and Sure (2012) 77.52%. The difference in hygiene condition in these various areas may account for the variation in the parasites carriage rate among different setting.

Findings from this study revealed that the mechanical transmission potential of cockroaches were significantly associated with the source of sampling site in the study. The higher number of cockroaches recorded with pit latrine is understandable because of the fact that cockroaches are more accessible to pit latrine where contamination with faecal matter is most likely.

However, that pit latrine are followed by kitchen was quiet alarming. Similar findings were observed by Etim (2013) in which more parasites were isolated from cockroaches found in the pit latrine. People have to be careful not to allow cockroach's accessibility to kitchens, as they have the potential to mechanically vector and transmit parasites. They should also ensure they cover food and food utensil to reduce the rate of transmission of parasites by cockroach. From this investigation it can be concluded that 29.71% of cockroach's population was contaminated. After feeding, they rest in the area and contaminate the environment with infective matter carried on the body surface, they can transmit the infection to the community at the rate of 29.71%. The cyst of *E. histolytica*, ova of *A. lumbricoides*, *T. trichuira* and eggs of Hook worm were observed in the external body parts of the cockroaches. The discovery of *A. lumbricoides*, *T. trichuira* on the insects supported the supposition that cockroaches play a significant role in the epidemiology of soil transmitting helminthes, which could carry and spread pathogens to other places, since they are able to travel up to 3 miles an hour from and to unsanitary sites (Lihoreau, & Rivault, 2009; Igbodika et al., 2019). Cockroaches constitute important reservoir of infectious pathogens and also transmit parasites; therefore, the control of cockroaches could substantially minimize the spread of infectious diseases.

5. Conclusion

This study has recorded moderate prevalence of medically important parasites on cockroaches. It has also related the parasites prevalence with sampling sites of the cockroaches and the house hold environmental hygiene. This suggests a possible role of this insect as a potential agent of mechanical transmission of parasitic diseases in the study area. To control these diseases, cockroaches in the human and animal habitations must be controlled by making the environment less favorable to them by the use of insecticides, gum traps, ensuring proper food storage facilities, and effective disposal of household refuse.

Recommendations

The following recommendation can be used to prevent transmission of parasites by cockroaches:

- Ensuring proper food storage
- Effective disposal of household refuse

- Use of insecticides, gum traps and other preventive measures.
- Treating people infected with the parasite
- Creating awareness

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